

INNOVATIVE FORMS OF WORKING IN MUSIC LESSONS

Abdullayeva Aygul Maxan qizi¹

¹Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami
2nd year graduate student, majoring in "Music Education and Art"

Panjiyev Qurboniyoz Berdiyevich²

Research advisor

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences Professor of

²Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7370441>

Abstract: This article discusses the forms and methods of using innovative technologies in music education. Also, the theoretical importance of innovative technologies in education is highlighted.

Key words: Music education, innovative technology, pedagogy, educational forms, methodology.

One of the most important skills that every teacher should acquire at the present time is the ability to organize and conduct lessons based on pedagogical technologies. According to its composition, this skill is quite complex. For this:

In order to prepare students for innovative activities and to form related skills and qualifications, it is first necessary to be able to effectively use educational and cognitive activities, to get students to master the skills of using pedagogical technologies in the teaching of each subject. For example, during conducting training, "Student training", "I am a conductor", "Cluster", "Brainstorming", "Scarabey", "Discussion", "Communication", "Group lib work", "Working in small groups", "Individual work", "Dividing into differential groups", "Multimedia technology", "Concert lesson", "Problem situation" in the course of music history, "Quiz Lesson", "Question - Answer", "Continue the Tune", "Lesson Tour", "Competition Lessons" technologies can be used in teaching the instrument performance lesson and students can be prepared for such activities.

The technological preparation of students for pedagogical activity is important for the student to be able to consciously, reliably and successfully apply theoretical psychological, pedagogical and methodical knowledge acquired during training and practical training, pedagogical practices. depends on the aspect.

The main methods of preparing students for innovative technological activities in the educational process are the following:

1. Tasks given to students to develop certain skills and systematic implementation of their theoretical and practical mastery;
2. Independent practice of some methods of pedagogical technologies during the lesson in pedagogical practice;
3. The teacher constantly monitors the student's mastery of pedagogical technologies and the ability to apply them in practice, giving advice;
4. To discuss the acquired skills and qualifications of students in the use of pedagogical technologies in the classroom, in groups;
5. To teach students to observe and analyze their own work and the work of their peers, and to evaluate it;

6. Holding various contests and competitions among students, showing them examples of creative work, etc. k.

The teacher chooses the technology used in the lesson according to the content and topic of the lesson, in which the main focus and goal is to achieve a specific result. Of course, the knowledge level, interests and aspirations of the students are taken into account here. For example, it is possible to listen to a musical piece on a tape recorder, then discuss it, analyze it collectively around a round table, learn the necessary information about the piece (theoretical, badny-text) based on a free discussion. It is also possible to creatively use visual aids, handouts, various literature, and information sources.

Along with the teacher, it is necessary to plan the teaching process in advance.

In this process, the teacher should take into account the content of the educational material, the possibility of the class, and make the students the main driving force in the center of the lesson.

It is very important for the teacher to make a technological map of the future lesson in order to design the lesson to a level that can lead to a good result, because the technological map of the lesson is created based on the capabilities and needs of the students from each subject, each training feature. Creating such a technological map has its own complexities. For this, the teacher should be aware of pedagogy, psychology, special methodology, informatics and information technologies, as well as know a lot of methods and methods. Making each lesson colorfully interesting and meaningful depends to a large extent on the planned technological map of the lesson, which was carefully thought out from the beginning.

The advanced pedagogical technologies used in the course of the lesson help the students to think freely, creatively approach every issue, to feel responsibility, to work independently, to analyze, to make good use of scientific and methodological literature, textbooks, and the most important thing is to study science. , should strengthen their interest in acquiring knowledge and skills on the subject.

Monitoring students during the lesson is a separate process, which is carried out in accordance with the purpose and content of each lesson.

The most real and correct and effective form of control is self-control. It is equally necessary for the teacher and for the pupil or student.

A music teacher carries out educational and educational work at the same time. He should not only have extensive knowledge in his specialty, but should also have good knowledge of other subjects related to music, literature, visual arts. The worldview, understanding of thinking, loyalty to one's profession and continuous improvement of one's skills should be of the first level importance of a person who educates students musically, artistically, and aesthetically.

As we have already mentioned, a music teacher should have a good knowledge of playing instruments, playing musical instruments, vocal singing, and theoretical knowledge during the period of higher education. Because the melody and the song performed live are faster and more emotional. Live music and songs quickly attract the attention of students and create a good mood. Allows you to repeat the beat (sentence) you want while singing as a group. And finally, a teacher who skillfully plays a musical instrument and sings a song in a beautiful voice shows his students how interesting and attractive it is to play music by everyone. The fact that a music teacher is not limited to skillfully playing musical instruments, but also has good sound, conducting skills, and teamwork skills guarantees the effectiveness of his work.

In addition, it is good for the teacher to monitor the lessons, recording his achievements and shortcomings in a special notebook, and prepare accordingly for the next lessons. Due to constant observations, the pedagogical skill of the teacher grows and develops. He learns to assess the situation, to feel the mood of students, how the lesson left an impression on them, their inner feelings. It is desirable that observation be carried out under the principle of "continuity" from the first grade to the seventh grade. In addition, in addition to the use of pedagogical technologies, in addition to self-performance, in each lesson, the content, authors, period of creation, genre, character, form, tempo, lad-tonality, should provide the necessary understanding of performance characteristics.

In the lesson of music culture, the teacher's vocabulary should be at a high level. The teacher's introduction about the studied work and the explanation of the subject of the lesson will bring the students into the wonderful and magical world of music. The main basis of such qualities, skills, qualifications are created in the educational process during the period of higher education and are continuously improved, enriched and developed in the teaching activity, which determines the main content of the social order placed on the professional activity of pedagogues - trainers. .

In this place, it is of particular importance to ensure the creative activity of students during musical lessons. Understanding music, enjoying its emotional impact depends on the participation of emotional feelings as well as knowledge, skills and abilities. The more active and deep the feelings are in the performance and perception of the work, the more conscious and effective their understanding and mastering, and being affected by them will be. These situations are a process that occurs as a result of creative activity. After all, boring and monotonous cannot create a lively emotional state in the classroom. Students' interest in the lesson depends primarily on the repertoire and methods (traditional or interactive methods) chosen for listening and performance. The main criterion of the repertoire of works selected for primary classes depends on their age, interest, knowledge and skills level.

Accordingly, the methods used should be more playful. The works related to the characters of fairy tales, animals, birds, plants, natural scenes, birds, which are organized in various competitions with the participation of dance, play, and thematic, are suitable for children's world. learns, develops aesthetic feelings, musical abilities. In this place, the use of modern songs as well as folk songs, works of brotherly peoples and composers makes the lessons more meaningful and active, and has a strong influence on the formation of feelings of love and affection for the heritage of folk music in young people. is enough. Creative activity occurs in every lesson.

Lessons of modern music culture can be considered an artistic-pedagogical work. Because the teacher creates it based on his individual creativity and experience. The composition and dramaturgy of the lesson, its interest in art-pedagogical students in music and educational materials, instilling in them the spiritual content of musical art and culture, understanding of modern musical creative activity - all this is the product of the creative approach of the teacher. is considered

When the teacher plans a music lesson (one hour), he determines the purpose, task, topic, type and forms of teaching, musical activities and the knowledge, methods, and technologies to be imparted to the students in their content, and then creates the scenario of the lesson. Each activity of the lesson: listening to music, singing as a team, musical literacy, rhythmic movements, accompaniment on musical instruments, games - should be connected and

integrated. Various technologies, tools, methods and methods are used to actively involve students in the lesson.

It is known that any pedagogical technology is based on educational principles that develop a new project of education and should be directed to the personality of the student. Cooperation between teacher and student, students and teacher should be organized on the basis of modern requirements. In this process, the skills of working in cooperation with students are formed. In contrast to the methodical development of the educational process, which is aimed at the active and effective activity of students, the pedagogical technology of education focuses on learners, as well as their individual and joint activities with the teacher. creates conditions for mastering the material.

The choice of the type of pedagogical technology depends on what level of knowledge and skills is intended to be mastered in the lessons and training.

There are many technologies used in the teaching process. These technologies will be designed for the age characteristics of students, mass education or individual training.

Currently, the interest in applying new pedagogical technologies to the educational process is growing day by day. Because pedagogical technology and interactive methods make it easy and convenient for young students to acquire thorough knowledge and skills. Here we briefly touch on some of the technologies that we have used in our practical experience.

References:

1. Atayeva N., Salayeva M., Hasanov S. General pedagogy. T., 2013.
2. Avliyakov N., Musaeva N. Pedagogical technologies. T., 2008.
3. Mavlonova R., Vahidova N., Rahmonkulova N. Pedagogical theory and history. "Science and Technology" T., 2010.
4. Mahmudov A.Kh. Competency approach to continuous education process didactic foundations of implementation // Lifelong education. 2012 #4. 8-12 pages
5. Choriev R. New pedagogical technologies - education - education quality and efficiency factor. Tashkent-2010.
6. Kharatova Shakhlo "USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS" Science and Education ISSUE 3, March 2022;